

NOTES

Complexes of Pd(II) and Pt(II) with Some Organic Ligands

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THE complexes of Pt(II) display various physiological properties¹ and have been studied widely²⁻⁴.

In the present communication I am reporting the preparation and characterisation of diacido complexes of Pd(II) and Pt(II) with 2-aminopyrimidine (AP) and 2-amino-4-methylpyrimidine (AMP) of formula $[M(AP/AMP)_2X_2]$ ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+} and $X = Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- or NCS^-) and neutral bis chelates $[ML_2]$ ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}) with LH = 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)imidazoline (HOPIMz), -benzimidazole (HOPBz), -benzoxazole (HOPBOX) and -benzothiazole (HOPBT).

Preparation of complexes :

$[M(AP/AMP)_2Cl_2]$, ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}): An aqueous acidic solution of $PdCl_2$ (pH 3-4) was refluxed with an ethanolic solution of appropriate ligands (1 : 2.5 molar ratio) on a steam bath for a few minutes when a cream yellow precipitate of the dichloro complex separated gradually. In case of Pt(II)⁵ the complex was obtained on concentration and cooling the refluxate to a small volume. The complexes were filtered, washed with water and dried in air.

$[M(AP/AMP)_2X_2]$, ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+} and $X = Br^-$, I^- , NO_2^- or NCS^-): These complexes were prepared by refluxing an aqueous suspension of the dichloro complexes $M(AP/AMP)_2Cl_2$, ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}) with an excess of sodium or potassium salts of appropriate anions on a steam bath for about 2 hr. Palladium(II) complexes separated in hot, while Pt(II) complexes were obtained on concentrating the refluxate to a small volume and cooling.

$[ML_2]$, ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+} and LH = HOPIMz, HOPBz, HOPBOX and HOPBT): An aqueous ethanolic solution of palladium(II) chloride was refluxed on a steam bath with appropriate ligand (about 1 : 2 molar ratio), by adjusting the pH of the reaction mixture with a dilute solution of NaOH to 5-6, for about half an hour when orange yellow or cream yellow complexes separated out gradually. In case of Pt(II) the pH of reaction mixture was raised to 8-9 by adding dilute solution of NaOH. The complexes separated when the refluxate was concentrated and pH was adjusted to 6-7 by adding dilute HCl. The products were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in an air oven at 70-80°.

The results of elemental analysis of the complexes are in good agreement with proposed formulae.

Results and Discussion

The complexes of both Pd(II) and Pt(II) are diamagnetic, suggesting their square planar stereochemistry. The solid reflectance spectra of the complexes do not display distinct electronic bands⁶ rather they display a broad shoulder near 380-420 nm in Pd(II) complexes and at 370-380 nm in Pt(II) complexes assignable to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{1g}$ transition in square planar arrangement of ligand molecules around metal atoms⁴. The DMF solutions of the complexes are almost non-conducting ($\Lambda_M = 3-6 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$) supports their nonionic character.

IR spectra: From infrared spectral studies of the metal complexes of HOPIMz, HOPBz, HOPBOX and HOPBT the coordination of these ligands have been suggested through the deprotonated phenolic oxygen and tertiary nitrogen of imidazoline, -benzimidazole, -benzoxazole and -benzothiazole part of the ligand molecules^{6,7}. The disappearance of (OH) stretching vibrations⁸ of HOPIMz (2690 cm^{-1}), HOPBz (254 cm^{-1}), HOPBOX (2280 cm^{-1}) and HOPBT (2260 cm^{-1}) suggests the bonding of the ligand molecules through deprotonated phenolic oxygen in these complexes. The (CN) stretching band of the ligands^{6,7} in these complexes is shifted to lower frequencies by 10-32 cm^{-1} than those of the free ligands, as usually observed for N-bonded ligand having (CN) nitrogen of free ligand involved in strong hydrogen bonding⁶⁻⁸.

2-Aminopyrimidine exhibits NH_2 symmetric stretch at 3170 cm^{-1} and asymmetric stretch at 3320 cm^{-1} . In complexes, the symmetric N-H vibration shifts to lower frequency by 20-60 cm^{-1} while asymmetric band splits into two medium bands observed at 3270-3300 and $3390 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The (N-H) symmetric stretch of AMP located at 3160 cm^{-1} also shifts to lower wave number by 10-30 cm^{-1} and asymmetric stretch (3335 cm^{-1}) splits into two bands in its complexes and observed at 3430 ± 10 and $3340 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The N-H degenerate deformation vibration of AP (1482 cm^{-1}) as well as of AMP (1470 cm^{-1}) is raised to higher wave number by 10-25 cm^{-1} in most of the complexes. Thus, the lowering of $\nu_s(NH)$ band and the blue shift of (N-H) deformation vibrations suggest the coordination of ligand molecules through amino nitrogen in these complexes⁹. The splitting of $\nu_{as}(NH_2)$ band can

be attributable to *cis* bonding of ligand molecules in the complexes.

The ir spectra of $[M(AP/AMP)_2(SCN)_2]$ ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}) exhibit a strong and sharp band at 2115-2122 cm^{-1} and weak band at 2085-2100 cm^{-1} (Table 1) attributable to $\nu(C=N)$ stretch of coordinated thiocyanate group¹⁰⁻¹¹. The $\nu(C=S)$ stretching band located near 680-710 cm^{-1} (Table 1)

TABLE-1

Complexes	$\nu(C=N)$ in cm^{-1}	$\nu(C=S)$ in cm^{-1}
$[Pd(AP)_2(SCN)_2]$	2120 s. sp. 2090 w	680 w
$[Pd(AMP)_2(SCN)_2]$	2115 s. sp. 2085 w	710 w
$[Pt(AP)_2(SCN)_2]$	2122 s. sp. 2100 w	705 w
$[Pt(AMP)_2(SCN)_2]$	2118 s. sp. 2090 w	710 w

indicates the S-bonding of thiocyanate group in these thiocyanato complexes^{12,13}. The bonding of thiocyanate group through sulphur atom in complexes is consistent with class 'b' character of Pt(II) and Pd(II).

In the ir spectra of $[M(AP/AMP)_2(NO_2)_2]$ ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}) the $\nu_{as}(NO_2)$ as well as $\nu_s(NO_2)$ vibration is raised to higher frequencies (Table 2)

TABLE-2

Compound	$\nu_{as}(NO_2)$ in cm^{-1}	$\nu_s(NO_2)$ in cm^{-1}	$\delta(ONO)$ in cm^{-1}
$[Pt(AP)_2(NO_2)_2]$	1400 vs. br	1305 vs 1268 s	885 s
$[Pt(AMP)_2(NO_2)_2]$	1415 s. br	1336 vs 1270 s	890 s
$[Pd(AP)_2(NO_2)_2]$	1405 vs. br	1340 s 1275 s	828 s
$[Pd(AMP)_2(NO_2)_2]$	1400 vs. br	1318 s 1282 s	838 s 818 s

vs=very strong; br=broad and s=strong.

suggesting that NO_2 group is coordinated through nitrogen atom in these complexes¹⁴. The $\nu_s(NO_2)$ vibration of the complexes has been found to split into two bands similar to *cis* bonded nitro group in square planar dinitro complexes¹⁵.

Thus, on the basis of above results, it is inferred that in diacido complexes $M(AP/AMP)_2X_2$ ($X = Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- or SCN^- and $M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}), the anions are bonded in *cis* position and ligands are coordinated to metal atom through amino nitrogen as unidentate molecules.

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Molecular Complex of 8-Hydroxyquinoline and Potassium Hexacyanoferrate(II) in Acid Medium

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SAHA and Saha¹ described the molecular complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine) and potassium hexacyanoferrates(II and III) respectively prepared in dilute aqueous acetic acid medium; the compositions of the complexes were given as $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 2$ oxine and $K_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 2$ oxine respectively. A glance at the formulae given raised some doubt in our mind as to what could be the binding forces to make the complexes so stable and we decided to study the first complex independently.

Experimental

All chemicals used in the work were of AnalaR/GR quality. The complex was prepared following the method¹ by dissolving 10.0 g $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$ in 30 ml of water and 6.86 g of oxine in 37 ml of dilute (5 M) acetic acid, and mixing the two solution with stirring; the chocolate coloured complex formed immediately was filtered in sintered gooch crucible, washed with water and dried in vacuum desiccator over KOH; yield 9.0 g. No HCN liberated during the preparation of the complex.

Results and Discussion

In contrast to the belief of Saha and Saha, the complex does not contain any appreciable amount of potassium (<0.01%) and does not give the flame test for potassium. This result leads one to believe that the complex is formed between hexacyanoferric(II) acid $[H_4Fe(CN)_6]$ and oxine. To have an

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